

See discussions, stats, and author profiles for this publication at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/357861142>

DESIGN & FABRICATION OF A SMART AUTOMOTIVE BRAKING SYSTEM

Conference Paper · December 2021

CITATIONS

0

READS

128

3 authors, including:

Md Nazim Uddin

Chittagong University of Engineering & Technology

1 PUBLICATION 0 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Mohammad Imran Bappy

Hyundai Heavy Industries

5 PUBLICATIONS 0 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

DESIGN & FABRICATION OF A SMART AUTOMOTIVE BRAKING SYSTEM

¹MD. NAZIM UDDIN, ²MOHAMMAD IMRAN BAPPY, ³MUHAMMAD SAMIUL ISLAM

^{1, 2, 3}, Research Scholar, Department of Mechanical Engineering, Chittagong, Bangladesh.

Email: ¹mdnazimxl@gmail.com, ²imran.cuet.bd@gmail.com, ³samiulislamsaif2015@gmail.com

Abstract: The braking system is one of the major aspects of an automobile. Even though the main function of a braking system is to work manually controlled by the driver, but in this study, an automatic braking system is introduced using an IR sensor. The sensor induced system is used for more effective and precise where human effort can be prone to error as resulting accidents. In this study, IR sensor-based feedback system is used to stop the vehicle from braking. Activating the braking system against different distances, with the IR sensor, results in avoiding collisions.

Index terms: IR sensor, microcontroller, Braking system, Bluetooth.

I. INTRODUCTION

One of the most important parts of an automobile is the braking system which is used for controlling the motion of a vehicle. The braking system has the role of reducing the velocity of a vehicle that is in motion. Uncontrollable or over speed can cause serious damage to both life forms and assets. It is statically seen that incidents involving a reversing vehicle cause serious injuries or fatalities up to 20-30% of all reported accidents [1].

Thus, the braking system of a vehicle is needed to be efficiently working and controllable in any circumstance. But the system mainly depends on the driver when it is working manually. As humans are prone to error it is quite difficult for using the brake to avoid dangerous situations right at the moment. Therefore, a braking system needs to be introduced which is automated and can activate itself immediately.

Automated braking systems need to have the facility be altered when an obstacle is nearby rather than only a trigger alarm system. This system works automatically by sensing the around atmosphere and is independent of the driver's actions. The time requirement of braking between human and automated braking systems has a drastically huge difference [2]. Also, the system is reliable to activate the braking system according to the need even if in driver's total concentration. The device is as much as helpful regardless of the driver's skill of operating the vehicle in a certain critical situation.

II. METHODOLOGY

The purpose of this project is to use IR Sensor to operate the braking system. The IR sensor only acts when it will detect any obstacle near the vehicle

according to the mounting. The system is mainly consisting of an IR emitter and receiver with a microcontroller, a feedback signal is used as an actuator for the DC Motor to stop immediately that driving the vehicle. Fig 3.1 shows a block diagram that needs to be executed to activate the automatic braking system.

Figure 1: Block Diagram of the Braking System

The block diagram illustrates the main sections of the intelligent braking system. The electric power supply is needed for the operation of Motors, Braking system control unit and IR sensor. IR transmitter and IR receiver are the modules of the main IR Sensor. IR transmitter emits infrared rays continuously. As the car gets too close to an obstacle, the Infrared rays reflect which was then received by the IR receiver. Reflected signal impulses the control unit to activate the braking system immediately. Then the control unit use response from the micro-controller to stop the motor hence actuating the brake. These actions are generated by the electronic signal hence electric power supply is mandatory for the processes [3].

III. COMPONENTS

1. Chasis Body: A Chassis of a 4-wheeled car is used in this experiment. The chassis is the basement for all the components mounted for the car. Components are screwed or glued on the chassis base to work as a whole vehicle body. Table 3.1 represents the specifications and parts are used for the chassis to build.

Table-1: Technical Specification of the Chassis

Parts	No of Parts	Specifications
Acrylic Chassis	2	255 mm * 155 mm * 65 mm
Acrylic Joints	8	T-type
Copper column	6	30 mm
Wheels	4	65mm (diameter)

2. Breadboard: A simple breadboard, made of white ABS plastic with black legend, is used in this experiment. The breadboard provides temporary connection points among the components. The breadboard also conducts low voltage, low currents and low power. The maximum output current is less than 700 mA.

3. Microcontroller (Arduino UNO): The control unit (CU) for the vehicle and IR System Circuit to connect each other is mainly depends on the processor. Arduino Uno is selected to use in this project. Arduino UNO has a microcontroller circuit board that is mainly developed on ATmega328P. It included 6 analogue inputs, 14 digital input/output pins (as 6 of them can be used as PWM outputs), a USB connection, a 16 MHz quartz crystal, an ICSP header, a power jack and a reset button [4]. It can be customized by using Arduino software.

4. Motor Driver Shield: A motor driver shield, model of L298N, is used which quite enables the proficiency of running 4 motors all at a time easily. The shield is directly connected to the power system as a battery to use the maximum power needed during the motor driving event generating torque to move the vehicle along the direction of the command.

5. Bluetooth Module: The Bluetooth module of HC-05 is used for connecting the whole system to the commendable software system. As the module receives the signal from an android device via Bluetooth, it sends the corresponding signal to the Arduino board to process and initiate the further step need to take.

Table-2: Technical Specification of Bluetooth Module (HC-05)

Specification	Value	Specification	Value
Default Bluetooth name	HC-05	Default firmware	LINVOR
Default password	1234 or 0000	Default mode	Date mode
Default communication	slave	Range	<100m

6. IR Sensor Unit: IR sensor model of FC-51 which is a combination of IR transmitter and IR receiver are used to detect the position of the obstacle. These sensors are mounted at the front side keeping absolute distance from each other on the vehicle. IR Sensor has multiple parts including IR Transmitter and Receiver with Power LED, Obstacle LED, 3 pins (VCC, GND, OUT) and a distant adjuster to regulate distance according to use.

7. DC Motor: Four DC gear motors are used in the design. , the main objective of using a DC motor is to move forward the vehicle with motion gained from the rotation of the DC motor. This motor rotates by using the Direct Current from the Motor Driver Shield connected with it. The power is supplied to the motor with the wired connection through the control unit.

8. Buzzer: A simple piezo active buzzer is used for generating alert sound when the IR Sensor detects an obstacle nearby within range. The buzzer creates a sound of min 85 dB.

9. Android Device: The purpose of the android device is to run the developed Bluetooth software as the command given by the micro-controller coding.

IV. ASSEMBLY OF COMPONENTS

The process starts with combining the different components altogether. The first step is to assembly the chassis. As the chassis used in the project were ready-made and hence needed assembly. Assembly is done by soldering the wire with the motor that is attached to the wheel socket. Also, the bolt-screw is available to make the double part chassis to be combined. The IR sensors, Motor Driver Shield and Bluetooth Module are fitted on the chassis surface with a glue gun. Manual switching is used to control the power supply to the main control system and 3 types of jumpers for wiring.

Figure 2: Circuit diagram of components mounted on vehicle

Figure 3: Prototype of Smart Automotive Braking system

V. CODING FOR MICRO-CONTROLLER AND BLUETOOTH SOFTWARE

The code for the micro-controller is built and tested for the system meshing with the circuit connection. The code is mainly written in C and C++ language using the application “Arduino IDE” [5]. The application is open-sourced, can be found on Arduino’s official website [6].

The code uploaded to the Micro-controller board is as follows:

```

1. char command;
2.
3. void setup(){
4. Serial.begin(9600);
5. pinMode(5, OUTPUT);
6. pinMode(8, INPUT);
7. pinMode(9, INPUT);
8. pinMode(10, OUTPUT);
9. pinMode(11, OUTPUT);
10. pinMode(12, OUTPUT);
11. pinMode(13, OUTPUT); }
12.
13. void loop(){
14. int obsf = digitalRead(8);
15. int obsb = digitalRead(9);
16.

```

```

17. if (obsf == LOW || obsb == LOW &&
Serial.available() ){
18. command = Serial.read();
19. Stop(); buzzer();}
20.
21. if(obsf == HIGH && obsb == HIGH &&
Serial.available()){
22. command = Serial.read();
23. switch(command){
24. case 'F': forward();break;
25. case 'B': back();break;
26. case 'L': left();break;
27. case 'R': right();break;
28. case 'G': forward(); left();break;
29. case 'T': forward(); right();break;
30. case 'H': back(); left();break;
31. case 'J': back(); right();break;
32. default : Stop(); break; } }
33.
34. void forward(){
35. digitalWrite(13,HIGH);
36. digitalWrite(12,LOW);
37. digitalWrite(11,HIGH);
38. digitalWrite(10,LOW); }
39.
40. void back(){
41. digitalWrite(13,LOW);
42. digitalWrite(12,HIGH);
43. digitalWrite(11,LOW);
44. digitalWrite(10,HIGH); }
45.
46. void left(){
47. digitalWrite(13,HIGH);
48. digitalWrite(12,LOW);
49. digitalWrite(11,LOW);
50. digitalWrite(10,LOW); }
51.
52. void right(){
53. digitalWrite(13,LOW);
54. digitalWrite(12,LOW);
55. digitalWrite(11,HIGH);
56. digitalWrite(10,LOW); }
57.
58. void Stop(){
59. digitalWrite(13,LOW);
60. digitalWrite(12,LOW);
61. digitalWrite(11,LOW);
62. digitalWrite(10,LOW); }
63.
64. void buzzer(){
65. tone(5, 500);
66. delay(500);
67. noTone(5);
68. delay(500);}

```

After setting up the micro-controller, an application named “Bluetooth RC Controller” [7] is installed on an android device to send a signal to the micro-controller. The application is an open-sourced application and can be found on “Google Play Store”. A Bluetooth connection between Android and Microcontroller is established by pairing both of the devices using the Bluetooth application. Then the application is enabled to send a signal to the Bluetooth Module which is connected with a

microcontroller. Thus, Micro-controller can execute certain types of commands according to the signal sent from the graphical user input-based controller application.

VI. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The braking distance is the main factor considered in this system. The result of this experiment is measured through the data collected from the trial of the vehicle during its working condition.

The theoretical value of the vehicle braking distance is calculated by using the following formula,

$$\text{Braking distance, } d = \frac{v^2}{2 * \mu * g}$$

The experimenting DC motors have the value of the speed is 39 m/min or 0.65 ms⁻¹ and the friction coefficient is 0.7 for the dry surface. Respected values are put into the equation to determine the theoretical value of braking distance.

$$\text{Braking distance, } d = \frac{0.65 * 0.65}{2 * 0.7 * 9.81} = 0.03076 \text{ m}$$

$$\text{Or, } d = 3.076 \text{ cm}$$

The braking distance is measured from the front and backward IR sensor separately. The data collection and calculations are done through manual instruction. IR sensor has a controllable varying distance to determine object distance can be changed through manual screw mounted on IR Sensor board. The detection range of the IR sensor varies from 2 cm to 30 cm as mentioned in the following table.

Table 3: Object detecting data with performance

IR sensor range (cm)	Object distance from vehicle before Brake (cm)	Object distance from vehicle after Brake (cm)	Distance travelled by vehicle AB-BB (cm)	Brake Performance
2	30	0	30	Failed
6	30	5	25	Activated
10	30	8	22	Activated
14	30	12.5	17.5	Activated
18	30	17.5	12.5	Activated
22	30	20	10	Activated
26	30	24.5	5.5	Activated
30	>30	29	>1	Activated

Figure 4: IR Sensor Range vs Object Distance Comparison Chart

VII. CONCLUSION

The outcome obtained from this project is the successful fabrication and application of activating the braking system for a vehicle using an IR sensor to sense the obstacle. When the distance between the vehicle and the object is decreasing continuously at a rapid rate, the active brake assist system comes into play. The braking arrangement is in action with the proper automation of brake boosting, as the distance is in decreasing manner. This reduces the overall braking distance. It will convey many hazardous accidents which can severely damage human life, vehicle and environmental resources. The ranging accuracy of the IR sensor in this prototype is about 2 cm to 30 cm and works effectively within the prescribed limit. This method is eco-friendly and this process is an effort to reduce accidents also in critical driving conditions.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors would like to express their heartfelt gratitude to the respondents for providing their priceless suggestions, comments and laboratory facilities through this research work.

REFERENCES

- [1] "Road traffic injuries," World Health Organization. [Online]. Available: <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/road-traffic-injuries>. [Accessed: 10-Aug-2021].
- [2] M. A. Abu, Z. Kornain, M. H. Rosli, and I. M. Iqbal, "Automated car braking system USING LABVIEW," 2012 IEEE Symposium on Industrial Electronics and Applications, 2012.
- [3] H. Kaleli, "New Universal Tribometer as Pin or Ball-on-Disc and Reciprocating Pin-on-

Plate Types,” Tribology in Industry, pp. 235–240, 2016.

- [4] “Arduino Uno REV3,” Arduino Uno Rev3 | Arduino Official Store. [Online]. Available: <https://store.arduino.cc/usa/arduino-uno-rev3>. [Accessed: 10-Aug-2021].
- [5] “Read this first,” Arduino Playground - Eclipse. [Online]. Available: <https://playground.arduino.cc/Code/Eclipse>. [Accessed: 10-Aug-2021].
- [6] “Aduino Webpage,” Arduino. [Online]. Available: <https://www.arduino.cc/en/Main/Software>. [Accessed: 10-Aug-2021].
- [7] Bluetooth RC car. [Online]. Available: <https://sites.google.com/site/bluetoothrccar>. [Accessed: 10-Aug-2021].

